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The impact of subsoil management on the delivery of ecosystem services: An economic valuation for Germany

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Title The impact of subsoil management on the delivery of ecosystem services:
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Abstract Agricultural practices, including subsoil management, can contribute to positive or negative changes in ecosystem performance. This study assessed the societal costs and benefits of two subsoil management measures (mechanical and biological amelioration), which are determined by an increase or decrease in the provision of soil-related ecosystem services. To estimate the monetary value of the considered soil ecosystem services, a Benefit Transfer exercise was applied, in which existing valuation studies were used to transfer and apply individual ecosystem service values to the management context of this study. The results show that ecosystem service delivery can be enhanced by 54% through mechanical soil management and by 23% through biological subsoil management. Even though the results should be considered as a rough estimate, they can help to increase awareness of the effects of alternative agriculture management practices, informing policy makers and help establishing policy instruments for the support of sustainable soil management measures in Germany.

Keywords BonaRes, subsoil, ecosystem services, economic valuation, bioeconomy, Soil³

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The impact of subsoil management on the delivery of ecosystem services: An economic valuation for Germany

Sophie Ittner, Holger Gerdes and Zoritzia Kiresiewa

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1 Introduction

The subsoil can be of significant importance for agricultural production as it holds large reserves of water, carbon and nutrients and could therefore help to increase and stabilise yields (Gaiser et al., 2012; Kautz et al., 2013; Lynch & Wojciechowski, 2015; Schneider & Don, 2019a; Schneider & Don, 2019b). The integration of subsoil into agricultural management could be particularly important given increased crop failures caused by hot and dry summers due to climate change (Gaiser et al., 2012; Kautz et al., 2013; Lynch & Wojciechowski, 2015). Therefore, the long-term research project Soil³ aims to contribute to a sustainable subsoil management by developing and testing the following measures:

- improving subsoil properties through the cultivation of deep-rooting pre-crops e.g. alfalfa [biological amelioration].
- deep loosening combined with the incorporation of compost into deep soil layers (DLC) [mechanical amelioration].

Agricultural practices, including subsoil management, can contribute to positive or negative changes in ecosystem performance (ecosystem services - ESS). Thus, agricultural management may lead to societal costs or generate societal benefits. To identify trade-offs and the associated changes in societal benefits, it is important to consider the entire spectrum of ecosystem services provided by the agro-ecological system in question. This paper addresses the question of how the changes in various services can be recorded and compared. It assesses the societal costs and benefits of subsoil management as determined by an increase or decrease in the provision of soil-related ESS. The focus is on the economic value of the soil ecosystem in agriculture, which is influenced by the subsoil.

A uniform value basis is required to make an overall assessment. Determining monetary values for all ecosystem services, regardless of whether or not they have an inherent market value, is one possibility. The Total Economic Value (TEV) concept currently serves as the most widely recognised basis for capturing environmental values in economic terms. The role of the subsoil in shaping the TEV of a soil ecosystem in an agricultural context is depicted in figure 1.

Figure 1: Contribution of the subsoil to the Total Economic Value of a soil ecosystem in an agricultural context (adapted from Turner et al., 2000). Colours represent the relevance of the subsoil. Dark green: high relevance of the subsoil; Green: moderate relevance; Light green: slight relevance or possibly relevant; White: no relevance (see also Ittner et al., 2020).

The assessment of ecosystem services, especially in combination with economic valuation, can be used for cost-benefit analyses of projects and policies and is particularly helpful in raising awareness and supporting decision and policy-making (Bartkowski et al., 2020; TEEB, 2016; LfU, 2019). An adequate understanding of the potential as well as the limitations of economic valuation is necessary if it is to serve as a basis for political decision-making processes (Bartkowski et al., 2020). While there is already a large number of studies that value individual soil-based ecosystem services (see ANNEX 6.1), there are few studies that consider the overall economic value of the soil ecosystem (Jónsson, 2016; Dominati et al., 2014; Porter et al., 2009; Sandhu et al., 2008; Fan et al., 2016).

In the context of the Soil³ project, we assessed the relevance of the subsoil in providing ecosystem services by conducting a survey with 57 experts from different disciplines (agronomy, soil sciences, microbiology, soil chemistry, etc.). Provision of food, filtering of nutrients and contaminants, flood mitigation and water retention, carbon storage and climate regulation, scientific and educational value as well as provision of raw materials were identified as those soil-related ESS for which the subsoil is most relevant (Ittner et al., 2020). In the subsequent analysis, we only focused on the ESS that were rated as highly or moderately relevant by the experts (see figure 1). Finally, an assessment of changes in ESS caused by the management measures investigated in the project was carried out for those ESS for which quantifiable indicators were available within the project (see chapter 2.3). Therefore, the calculations made here do not represent the Total Economic Value of a soil ecosystem, but only a part of it.

2 Methods

The methods applied in our study relate to a Benefit Transfer exercise, which we conducted to estimate the economic value of projected changes in ecosystem service delivery caused by subsoil management, i.e. through the application of the Soil³ method (DLC) and through biological amelioration on suitable agricultural areas in Germany. Due to resource limitations, the design and implementation of primary valuation studies was not feasible in the context of the Soil³ project. We therefore applied the Benefit Transfer technique, which uses existing valuation studies to transfer and apply individual ecosystem service values to the relevant policy or management context. In our case, this required 1) the identification and review of existing soil valuation studies, 2) the identification of suitable areas for subsoil management in Germany, 3) the analysis of effects of subsoil management on the delivery of ecosystem services, and 4) the economic valuation of projected marginal changes by means of a simplified unit value transfer. In the following subchapters, the different steps are described in detail.

2.1 Identification and review of soil valuation studies; creation of a valuation database

To enable comprehensive identification and evaluation of relevant studies that might provide a meaningful basis for the Benefit Transfer, we created a database of relevant primary valuation studies. This database is based on the overview offered by Jónsson and Davíðsdóttir (2016) who provide a comprehensive table of soil ESS valuation studies with respective information on time-, area- or mass-related monetary values. We assessed this table for completeness and updated it with more recent studies covering the years 2014-2019. As a starting point, we used the Environmental Valuation Reference Inventory (EVRI). Within the EVRI database we performed a search with the following specifications: keyword = soil; study type = primary; region = any; environmental assets = any. This search resulted in 29 records. A complementary web search yielded 51 additional valuation studies that could potentially be used for the Benefit Transfer. We then refined this total selection of 80 studies by adopting the following criteria:

- study performed within OECD member state or China or Mexico (i.e. the review was limited to local contexts which feature socio-economic characteristics that are similar to the ones of our policy site);
- primary literature (i.e. only peer-reviewed scientific publications were considered);

- value given as currency with time, area/mass relation (i.e. only values expressed in currency unit per spatial unit per time unit were considered);
- valuation of soil-related ecosystem services (i.e. valuations of ecosystem services not directly related to a soil ecosystem context were not considered).

The application of these criteria led to two eligible studies from EVRI and eight studies from the web search. Combined with the 33 studies included in the review by Jónsson and Davíðsdóttir (2016), our initial valuation database contained 43 primary valuation studies.

In a next step, these studies were assessed to determine whether the existing values were transferable to our policy site (Germany) as part of a Benefit Transfer exercise. The suitability of a study for Benefit Transfer was assessed based on three criteria:

- a) comparability of the ecosystem service;
- b) comparability of the indicator used in the study to assess the ecosystem service;
- c) indication of the value in hectares.

All selected studies were assessed in terms of scientific soundness based on the type of study approach (e.g. own field assessment or modelling) and calculation details of the individual ecosystem service. Of the 43 soil valuation studies identified, 11 of which provided a total of 22 values were considered useful for the assessment of the set of ecosystem services investigated in this study.

In a final step, the 22 original values were converted into euros and further adjusted by accounting for historical inflation. For currency conversion, the publication year of the study (i.e. the official exchange rate on 31 December of the respective year) was considered using the OANDA currency converter¹. Subsequently, the historical inflation rate was calculated for each value using consumer price index data (reference year 2021)².

2.2 Identification of suitable areas for subsoil management in Germany

The Benefit Transfer carried out here is based on the assessment of changes in ESS through subsoil management per hectare. Therefore, a target area in hectares is needed as a basis on which the investigated measures can be implemented. The suitability of implementing different subsoil amelioration measures is region-specific and depends on the natural-spatial conditions of the region such as geogenic, pedogenic and climatic factors. Both the need and the capability of the soil to be meliorated were considered. Schneider (2020) conducted an assessment of environmental constraints in Germany such as soil properties and climate and found that mechanical amelioration (DLC) is best suited for relatively dry regions with sandy soils in Northeastern Germany. In contrast, biological amelioration may have the strongest positive effects in Central and Southern Germany (see Schneider 2020 and figure 2). Based on these maps, we determined the hectares for the two amelioration techniques for each federal state.

¹ <https://www.oanda.com/currency-converter/>

² <https://www.inflationtool.com/euro/>

Federal state	Method	Area in ha	% of UAA
BB	DLC	520000	36%
	Biological	50000	3%
BW	DLC	420000	26%
	Biological	370000	23%
BY	DLC	1050000	32%
	Biological	830000	25%
HE	DLC	290000	33%
	Biological	200000	23%
MV	DLC	230000	16%
	Biological	50000	3%
NI	DLC	410000	15%
	Biological	160000	6%
NW	DLC	240000	15%
	Biological	200000	12%
RP	DLC	210000	26%
	Biological	110000	14%
SH	DLC	100000	9%
	Biological	60000	6%
SL	DLC	50000	45%
	Biological	50000	45%
SN	DLC	140000	14%
	Biological	120000	12%
ST	DLC	420000	34%
	Biological	170000	14%
TH	DLC	360000	43%
	Biological	200000	24%
DE	DLC	4440000	25%
	Biological	2570000	14%

Figure 2: Target areas for DLC (A) and biological (B) subsoil amelioration per federal state and in Germany based on Schneider (2020). Points show affected sites from the 8 x 8 km sampling grid of the German Agricultural Soil Inventory. Point size increases with decreasing mean annual water balance, which serves as an indicator for drought stress and indicates the need of the soil to be meliorated.

2.3 Analysis of effects of subsoil management on the provision of ecosystem services

Within the Soil³ project, we assessed six different ESS: 1) provision of food, feed and fibre, 2) carbon storage, 3) water retention and plant water availability, 4) Filtering of nutrients, 5) soil biology and 6) nutrient and organic compounds cycling. To quantify changes in the provision of ESS, the Soil³ project identified appropriate indicators based on the soil parameters studied (for further details see Ittner et al., 2020). We adapted and supplemented the list of Ittner et al. (2020) according to new insights and results (see table 1).

Table 1: Changes of soil-related ESS due to subsoil management

Ecosystem service	Indicator	Subsoil management technique	Change in %	Year after management	Source
Provision of food, feed and fibre	Yield [dt/ha]	DLC	+ 20%	1/2/3	Soil ³ project: Jakobs et al. (2019) + CF1; CF2; CF3 (unpublished)
		Biological amelioration	+ 5%	1	Soil ³ project: CF2 (unpublished)
Carbon storage	C storage [C/ha]	DLC	+ 14%	1	Soil ³ project: CF1 (unpublished)
		Biological amelioration	+ 5%	1	Athmann (unpublished) same study site as Soil ³
Water retention and plant water availability	Volumetric water content [%]	DLC	+ 10%	1/2/3	Soil ³ project: CF1 (unpublished)
		Biological amelioration	+ 118%	1	Gaiser et al. (2012); same study site as Soil ³
Filtering of nutrients	N-leaching [N _{min}]	DLC	+ 74%	1/2	Soil ³ project: Jakobs et al. (2019)
		Biological amelioration	+ 72%	1/2	Seidel et al. (2019); same study site as Soil ³
Soil biology	Earthworm abundance [numbers]	DLC	+ 50%	54	Athmann unpublished
		Biological amelioration	+ 300%	2-3	Sohlenius (1990)
Nutrient and organic compounds cycling	Microbial biomass [N _{mic}]	DLC	+ 400%	2	Soil ³ project: Jaiswal and Schulz (unpublished)
		Biological amelioration	+ 200%	5	Haynes (1999)

2.4 Economic valuation of marginal changes (Benefit Transfer)

A total of 22 monetary values which were considered useful for the assessment of marginal changes in ecosystem service provision caused by subsoil management were then used in the Benefit Transfer exercise (see chapter 2.1). Based on these 22 monetary values, an average value per hectare was calculated for four of the six relevant ecosystem services (see table 1). For the provision of food, feed and fibre, the average value is based on market values, while for carbon storage it is based on the social cost of carbon (UBA, 2020).

In our baseline scenario we assumed that standard agricultural practices without subsoil protection would be applied in areas potentially suitable for subsoil management (Figure 2). In our subsoil management scenario, the Soil³ technique would be applied on 4.4 million hectares and biological amelioration would be applied on 2.57 million hectares of agricultural land in Germany (see figure 2), resulting in projected changes in the delivery of soil-related ecosystem services as depicted in table 1.

Subsequently, a simplified unit value transfer was applied using the average monetary values for six relevant ecosystem services to estimate the economic value of the projected annual change in ecosystem service delivery caused by application of the Soil³ method and by application of the biological amelioration method, respectively. The economic value of the projected marginal changes was calculated on a per-hectare basis for 13 German federal states as well as for Germany as a whole, considering the areas which were identified as potentially suitable for subsoil management.

3 Results

3.1 Suitability of soil valuation studies

As mentioned in CH 2.1, 11 studies were considered useful for calculating the average monetary value of the ecosystem services assessed in this study. Table 2 shows which studies form the basis for calculating the respective ecosystem service, the study region, the valuation method used and the range of the underlying values of the publications considered. The assumptions underlying the calculation of monetary values for each ecosystem service are described below in detail.

Table 2: Overview and description of the basis for the calculation of the respective ecosystem services

ESS	Source	Indicator	Region	Valuation method	Value range [EUR/ha/y]
Provision of food, feed and fibre	Destatis, 2021; BMEL, Erntebericht 2020	Yield	Germany	Market price	1022
Carbon storage	UBA, 2020; BMEL, 2018	C-storage	Germany	Social cost of carbon	-136
Water retention and plant water availability	Kay et al., 2019; Pimentel et al., 1995	Water retention potential and irrigation cost	USA, Denmark	Replacement cost	41.7 - 63.9
Filtering of nutrients	Dominati et al., 2016; Fan et al., 2016; Dominati et al., 2014	Filtering of N	New Zealand, Greece, EU	Defensive expenditure	151.6 - 369.2
Biodiversity and soil biology	Porter et al., 2009; Sandhu, 2010; Sandhu, 2008; Pimentel et al., 1997	Soil formation by earthworms	USA, Denmark, New Zealand	Replacement cost /Market price	3.1 - 13.6
Nutrient and organic compounds cycling	Fan et al., 2016; Sandhu, 2015; Porter et al., 2009; Sandhu, 2010; Sandhu, 2008	Nitrogen mineralisation by soil microorganisms and invertebrates	Denmark, New Zealand	Replacement cost/ Market price	93.9 - 275.8

Provision of food, feed and fibre

The monetary valuation of this ESS is carried out using a price-based approach. This is one of the direct market valuation methods and uses market producer prices of the agricultural product to determine the monetary value of the supply service. Market prices are volatile, e.g. due to year-to-year or even monthly fluctuations in demand. We therefore used average market prices for feed barley from 2015 to 2020. For the economic valuation of the provision of food, feed and fibre, we multiplied the mean market price of fodder barley by the mean barley yield in dt/ha in the respective time period (2015-2020) in Germany. The

benefit of one hectare of agricultural land is thus assigned a value of EUR 1022 per year in terms of its function of providing food, feed and fibre.

Carbon storage

For the economic valuation of carbon storage, we used the monetary value for avoided carbon emissions. This regulating service of a soil to store carbon is here defined as the annual net C flow into soil e.g. through crop and root residues and does not include the carbon stock of the soil under consideration. Instead of using the C market price of about 25 EUR/t CO₂ to monetise this service, we used the damage costs determined by Germany's Federal Environment Agency which are published in the Methodological Convention 3.1 for the Determination of Environmental Costs (UBA, 2020). Here, a damage cost rate with a value of 195 EUR/t CO₂ eq is recommended for the year 2020. The measures of net C flows were converted to CO₂ equivalents and multiplied by the market price of CO₂. According to BMEL (2018), arable soils in Germany are net emitters of approx. 0.19 t/ha/a carbon on average. Therefore, we assume a negative ecosystem service as a baseline value here and costs of -136 EUR/ha/a.

Water retention and plant water availability

Fewer useful studies were available to evaluate water retention and plant water availability compared to the others. Most studies on water retention estimate the damage costs of flooding to evaluate the water retention of a landscape. However, this is not relevant to our assessment as we estimate the direct plant water availability in the soil. The two studies used to determine the economic value of soil water storage based their calculation on the ability of soils to store water and the costs of applying the same amount of water to the field. Based on different costs of irrigation water, the value ranges from 41.7 to 63.9 EUR/ha/y.

Filtering of nutrients Soils have the ability to prevent nitrate leaching and thus control water quality by preventing its release into water bodies (ground water, lakes and rivers). Two of the three studies used evaluated this service by calculating the costs of existing mitigation techniques to limit N-leaching (standoff pad, low N feed supplements and nitrification inhibitors) (Dominati et al., 2014; Dominati et al., 2016). Kay et al. (2019), on the other hand, based their calculation on the costs of reducing nitrate from wastewater. Filtering nitrate from wastewater seems to be cheaper than the costs of mitigation measures. Due to different technical approaches, the values vary more than for other ecosystem services (between 151.6 - 369.2 EUR/ha/y).

Biodiversity and soil biology

Soil life provides numerous ecosystem services. Soil formation is one of them, as is the provision of nutrients (see nutrient and organic compounds cycling). Earthworms are of particular importance in this respect. All studies used here based their economic valuation on the assumption that the mean biomass of an earthworm is 0.2 g and that 1000 kg of earthworms create 1000 kg of soil ha/y (Pimentel et al., 1995). Thus, the amount of topsoil created was calculated by multiplying earthworm mass by the price of topsoil in the country of study, which varies between regions.

Nutrient and organic compounds cycling

As part of the soil life, microorganisms are key components in the process of nutrient and organic compounds cycling. All studies used data on mineralisation of organic matter obtained from field experiments to assess the economic value of plant nutrient mineralisation by soil microorganisms. The total amount of mineralised nitrogen measured was valued at the equivalent price of N/kg. Estimates of the performance of microorganisms in terms of nutrient and organic compounds cycling vary and range from 93.9 - 275.8 EUR/ha/y.

3.2 Economic values of ecosystem services

Based on the monetary values of the identified studies (see chapter 3.1), an average value was calculated for each ecosystem service to serve as a basis for further calculations in this study. Table 3 shows the baseline ESS flow and the changed flows based on changes in the provision of ecosystem services due to the two subsoil management measures (see chapter 2.3). It can be seen that, compared to cropland, a higher value in terms of ecosystem services can be achieved through both subsoil management measures per hectare and year. While on average 1331 EUR/ha/yr is generated through soil ecosystem services on cropland, biological subsoil management would lead to an ecosystem service flow of 1640 EUR/ha/yr and DLC to 2052 EUR/ha/yr.

Table 3: Overview of monetary values for the respective ecosystem services and their changes due to the two subsoil management methods considered.

Ecosystem service	Baseline - Average value for cropland [EUR/ha/yr]	Average value with DLC [EUR/ha/yr]	Average value with biological amelioration [EUR/ha/yr]
Provision of food, feed and fibre	1022	1226 (+20%)	1073 (+5%)
Carbon storage	-136	-117 (+14%)	-130 (+5%)
Water retention and plant water availability	53	58 (+10%)	115 (+118%)
Filtering of nutrients	222	58 (-74%)	62 (-72%)
Biodiversity and soil biology	8	11 (+50%)	31 (+300%)
Nutrient and organic compounds cycling	163	816 (+400%)	489 (+200%)
SUM	1331	2052	1640

There are four studies that quantify the Total Economic Value for agricultural ecosystem services with a focus on soils. Table 4 provides an overview of the inflation-adjusted values of the ecosystem services examined in the identified studies compared to our study. No two studies quantify the exact same set of ecosystem services. Comparing the underlying values shows that the values used in this study are mostly lower than those of the other studies. Only Porter et al. (2009) provides a baseline value for all soil ecosystem services of only 706 EUR/ha, which is lower than the value used here, but does not include "Filtering of N". It should be noted that the economic valuation of "Provision of food, feed and fibre" varies widely. Dominati et al. (2014), for example, quantify this service at 4226 EUR/ha. Sandhu et al. (2008) also estimates this benefit to be much higher than in the present study, at 3017 EUR/ha, while Fan et al. (2016) estimate 1535 EUR/ha, which is closer to the value assumed here. The studies also differ fundamentally on the assumed effects of agricultural practices on soil carbon. While some assume that agricultural practices do not affect soil carbon (Dominati et al., 2014), others assume that soil carbon increases (Porter et al., 2009; Sandhu et al., 2008) or decreases (Fan et al., 2016).

Table 4: Comparison of the baseline values of our Soil³ study with other relevant economic valuation studies for agricultural ecosystem services

	Baseline – Soil ³ [EUR/ha]	Dominati et al., 2014 [EUR/ha]	Porter et al., 2009 [EUR/ha]	Sandhu et al., 2008 [EUR/ha]	Fan et al 2016., [EUR/ha]
Provision of food, feed and fibre	1022	4226	423	3017	1535
Carbon storage	-136	0	21	18	-27
Water retention and plant water availability	53	NA	71	67	65
Filtering of nutrients	222	492	NA	NA	NA
Biodiversity and soil biology	8	NA	14	5	NA
Nutrient and organic compounds cycling	163	NA	178	168	135
SUM	1331	4719	706	3275	1709

3.3 Extrapolation to regional level and total economic value

Based on the areas suitable for the respective subsoil melioration technique (see chapter 2.2), the changes in ecosystem services due to subsoil management (see chapter 2.3) and the average economic value for soil ecosystem services per hectare (see chapter 3.2), the current and the additional ESS flow was calculated in euros for each federal state and for Germany as a whole. In the baseline scenario, the current annual flow of ecosystem services amounts to €5.9 billion (see Table 5) for the area potentially suitable for DLC application, corresponding to 25% of the utilised agricultural area (UAA), and €3.4 billion (see Table 6) for the area potentially suitable for biological improvement, corresponding to 14% of the UAA.

The use of DLC on 25% of UAA can generate an additional economic value of almost 3.2 billion euros per year through enhanced ecosystem service delivery in Germany. The delivery of ecosystem services can thus be enhanced by 54% through mechanical soil management. This is mainly due to the improved performance in terms of nutrient component cycling by microorganisms and the yield-increasing effect (for more details see table 7 in Annex 6.2). The greatest potential is seen in Bavaria, followed by Brandenburg, Baden-Württemberg and Saxony-Anhalt.

Table 5: Results of extrapolation of additional annual ESS flows in euros for mechanical subsoil management (DLC)

Region	Suitable area (% of UAA)	Annual ESS flows (€) - current	Additional annual ESS flows (€) - after DLC	SUM with subsoil management
BB	36%	692,364,498	374,662,075	1,067,026,573
BW	26%	559,217,479	302,611,676	861,829,155
BY	32%	1,398,043,698	756,529,190	2,154,572,888
HE	33%	386,126,355	208,946,157	595,072,512
MV	16%	306,238,143	165,715,918	471,954,061
NI	15%	545,902,777	295,406,636	841,309,413
NW	15%	319,552,845	172,920,958	492,473,803
RP	26%	279,608,740	151,305,838	430,914,578
SH	9%	133,147,019	72,050,399	205,197,418

Region	Suitable area (% of UAA)	Annual ESS flows (€) - current	Additional annual ESS flows (€) - after DLC	SUM with subsoil management
SL	45%	66,573,509	36,025,200	102,598,709
SN	14%	186,405,826	100,870,559	287,276,385
ST	34%	559,217,479	302,611,676	861,829,155
TH	43%	479,329,268	259,381,437	738,710,705
DE (sum)	25%	5,911,727,638	3,199,037,717	9,110,765,356 (+54%)

On land suitable for biological amelioration (14% of the UAA), the cultivation of alfalfa can generate an additional economic value of almost 800 million euros per year through enhanced ecosystem service delivery. This translates to an increase of 23% compared to conventional cultivation without subsoil management. Again, the greatest effect is due to increased nutrient cycling performance. In addition, the increased water storage capacity and the yield-increasing effect have a positive impact (for more details see table 8 in Annex 6.2).

Table 6: Results of extrapolation of additional annual ESS flows in euros for biological subsoil management

Region	Suitable area (% of UAA)	Annual ESS flows (€) - current	Additional annual ESS flows (€) - after biological amelioration	SUM with subsoil management
BB	3%	66,573,509	15,433,273	82,006,782
BW	23%	492,643,970	114,206,218	606,850,188
BY	25%	1,105,120,257	256,192,328	1,361,312,584
HE	23%	266,294,038	61,733,091	328,027,129
MV	3%	66,573,509	15,433,273	82,006,782
NI	6%	213,035,230	49,386,473	262,421,703
NW	12%	266,294,038	61,733,091	328,027,129
RP	14%	146,461,721	33,953,200	180,414,921
SH	6%	79,888,211	18,519,927	98,408,139
SL	45%	66,573,509	15,433,273	82,006,782
SN	12%	159,776,423	37,039,855	196,816,277
ST	14%	226,349,932	52,473,127	278,823,059
TH	24%	266,294,038	61,733,091	328,027,129
DE (sum)	14%	3,421,878,385	793,270,219	4,215,148,605 (+23%)

4 Discussion and Outlook

4.1 Monetisation of ecosystem services

Quantifying the economic value of a soil-agro-ecosystem as part of a cost-benefit analysis has the potential to provide a holistic overview of the environmental performance of subsoil management. Even though the results are only a rough estimate (see also chapter 4.2). The ecosystem services quantified can vary depending on site and soil properties as biophysical processes of ecosystems act in different ways at each site. Moreover, ecosystem services are usually valued according to their benefits. For example, the benefits of improved soil water storage capacity will be higher in arid regions or in regions where soils have low water storage potential compared to regions with fewer limiting factors. Here, improved

performance would achieve higher economic value. However, these differences cannot be captured by the analysis presented. The approach shown is a site-independent valuation of ecosystem services. Nevertheless, the methodology used here is well suited for identifying and comparing the potential of different management measures as well as for identifying trade-offs. Although trade-offs often cannot be avoided in agricultural practice, their identification and quantification can contribute to better site-adapted management (TEEB, 2016).

Our study shows that subsoil management brings economic benefits to society beyond the positive impact on farm-level agricultural production. At the farm level, other studies of the Soil³ project have shown that improving water retention and root penetration is perceived as very important among farmers and other soil experts (Frelüh-Larsen et al., 2019; Hinzmann et al., 2021). In addition, ensuring a varied crop rotation, reducing yield fluctuation, and improving the living conditions for plants and animals in the soil are also considered to play a key role for the sustainable use of soils and agriculture (Hinzmann et al., 2021). The improvement of these ecosystem services was often discussed in the context of drought. Above all, improving water storage was described by farmers as an adaptation strategy to climate change and increasingly frequent droughts, which can then help to bridge temporary extreme deficits. In addition, the importance of water storage for flood control was emphasized. There was also wide agreement about the environmental benefits of alfalfa cultivation and its contribution to improved ESS such as water and nutrient provision (ibid.) Only the regulating service in terms of nutrient leaching is at risk of being reduced, whereby the actual N-leaching strongly depends on weather conditions and soil types. Nevertheless, there is a risk of a trade-off between increased provision of nutrients through increased nutrient component cycling and increased nitrogen leaching.

As mentioned above, there are only few studies that quantify the overall economic value of agricultural ecosystem services with a focus on soils (Dominati et al., 2014; Porter et al., 2009; Sandhu et al., 2008; Fan et al., 2016). No comparative studies exist for Germany and in all other studies, a link to subsoil is missing completely. This shows that the economic value of soils in Germany and in particular the economic value of subsoil and subsoil management has not yet been thoroughly researched.

4.2 Applicability of the Benefit Transfer method

As stated by Bartkowski et al. (2020), “the direct transfer of economic values from one study to another context is problematic.” The problems relate, for instance, to the quality and suitability of the primary valuation study (which often can only be superficially assessed) and to the applicability of the value estimates to the policy or management context in question (which might require profound adjustments due to divergent site conditions). The latter applies even more if the value estimates are not only transferred to an individual policy or management site, but are scaled up to the regional or national level.

In addition to the limitations and uncertainties associated with the identification and transfer of monetary value estimates, another uncertainty factor relates to the identification of the applicable management area in the baseline and subsoil management scenarios. The assessment is based on exclusion criteria defined by thresholds for soil properties and climatic conditions. Schneider (2020) pointed out that the disadvantage of this approach is that most thresholds are arbitrary and can vary within a certain range, which would change the results for individual sites. Furthermore, the results were clustered (e.g. less than 500 ha), which is why some federal states reported identical figures. This approach may be suitable for identifying target regions for subsoil melioration on federal state level, but may lead to uncertainties in calculating the ESS delivery potential.

Finally, the estimated effects of subsoil management on the provision of ecosystem services introduce another area of uncertainty. In our case, the estimated changes are based on the results of a central field experiment, supplemented by information that was retrieved from relevant scientific publications. Given the complexity of the subsoil in terms of ecological conditions and interaction with the overall soil ecosystem, the estimated changes should be considered as initial figures to be validated and supported by further research and monitoring.

In sum, due to the limitations elaborated above, a Benefit Transfer exercise is prone to uncertainties. However, we have demonstrated that under a condition where primary valuation studies cannot be conducted due to resource limitations, it can be a suitable means to estimate the large-scale socio-economic consequences resulting from large-scale application of a certain policy or management scheme. We were able to monetise the effects of subsoil management on ecosystem delivery at the national level in Germany as well as at the state level in 13 federal states. A communication and exploitation strategy targeting decision-makers at those levels must be based on transparency regarding the underlying assumptions and associated uncertainties.

4.3 Benefits of economic assessment for sustainable soil management and policy

The methodology used in this study to monetise agricultural ecosystem services in relation to different subsoil management practices is primarily intended to provide a holistic view in terms of their social value added or costs incurred. At the federal state level, quantifying the societal costs of subsoil management measures can be used to better assess the potential of different measures for the federal state. In Brandenburg, for example, the potential for improving soil ecosystem services is 20 times higher with mechanical subsoil management than with biological amelioration.

Bartkowski et al. (2020) state that economic valuation of soil-based ecosystem services may increase awareness of the importance and contribution of agriculture soils to human well-being. This method is therefore suitable for raising awareness of the role of subsoil management measures and, more importantly, for highlighting potential trade-offs at the societal level. In this sense, the results of our study also serve to inform political decision-makers and other social actors about the social relevance of subsoil management. Due to the spatial resolution and the generalised estimates made (see also 4.1), the target audience should rather be seen at the federal or state level. The results are less suitable to support farmers or practitioners in on-site management decisions where differences in e.g. site and soil properties play a central role.

Despite the inherent uncertainties (see also 4.2), the great added value of such studies is that non-monetary goods are naturally assigned a value that can be easily communicated. The figures shown here should be taken as indicative rather than absolute. As stated above, the uncertainties mentioned must be communicated transparently.

Bartowski et al. (2020) argue that economic valuation can play an important role in all phases of the policy process, from agenda setting, policy formulation and decision making, legitimation and implementation to evaluation and termination. This assumption is supported by several other studies, which state that economic valuation studies offer pathways for developing policy instruments for management practices that promote soil-based ecosystem services (e.g. Glæsner, Helming & De Vries, 2014; Turpin et al., 2017; Vrebos et al., 2017, Bartowski et al., 2020). However, to determine, e.g. payment levels based on such studies, much more precise economic estimates are needed that also take individual site conditions into account. Nevertheless, our results can be used to inform policy makers and help create instruments to support sustainable soil management measures that enhance soil-based ecosystem services.

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5 Literature

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6 ANNEX

6.1 Overview of identified soil valuation studies

Ref	Authors, Year of publication	Title, Place of publication
1	Bejranonda, S., Hitzhusen, F.J., 1996.	An assessment of soil erosion impacts on lakeside property values in Ohio: A hedonic pricing method (HPM) application. <i>Am J Agr Econ</i> 78, 1396-1396.
2	Bond, C.A., Hoag, D.L., Kipperberg, G., 2011.	Agricultural Producers and the Environment: A Stated Preference Analysis of Colorado Corn Producers. <i>Can J Agr Econ</i> 59, 127-144.
3	Colombo, S., Calatrava-Requena, J., Hanley, N., 2006.	Analysing the social benefits of soil conservation measures using stated preference methods. <i>Ecological Economics</i> 58, 850-861.
4	Daily, G.C., Matson, P.A., Vitousek, P.M., 1997.	Ecosystem services supplied by soil. In: Daily, G.C. (Ed.), <i>Nature's services: Societal dependence on natural ecosystems</i> . Island Press, Washington, DC, pp. 113-132.
5	Decaens, T., Jimenez, J.J., Gioia, C., Measey, G.J., Lavelle, P., 2006.	The values of soil animals for conservation biology. <i>Eur J Soil Biol</i> 42, S23-S38.
6	Dolley, T.P., Bolen, W.P., 2000.	Silica. <i>US Geological Survey Minerals Yearbook</i> . US Geological Survey.
7	Dominati, E. J., Mackay, A., Lynch, B., Heath, N., & Millner, I., 2014.	An ecosystem services approach to the quantification of shallow mass movement erosion and the value of soil conservation practices. <i>Ecosystem Services</i> , 9(0), 204-215.
8	Dominati, E., Mackay, A., Green, S., Patterson, M., 2014.	A soil change-based methodology for the quantification and valuation of ecosystem services from agro-ecosystems: A case study of pastoral agriculture in New Zealand. <i>Ecological Economics</i> 100, 119-129.
9	Drechsel, P., Giordano, M., Gyiele, L., 2004.	Valuing nutrients in soil and water: Concepts and techniques with examples from IWMI studies in the developing world. <i>International Water Management Institute</i> , Colombo, Sri Lanka.
10	Duffy, M., 2012.	Value of Soil Erosion to the Land Owner. <i>IOWA State University</i> Ames, Iowa.
11	Eade, J.D.O., Moran, D., 1995.	Spatial Economic Valuation: Benefits Transfer using Geographical Information Systems. <i>Journal of Environmental Management</i> .
12	Eastwood, C., Krause, M., Alexander, R.R., 2000.	Muddied Waters: Estimating the national economic cost of soil erosion and sedimentation in New Zealand.
13	Fan, F., Henriksen, C.B., Porter, J., 2016.	Valuation of ecosystem services in organic cereal crop production systems with different management practices in relation to organic matter input. <i>Ecosystem Services</i> , 22, 117-127.
14	Glenk, K., Colombo, S., 2011.	Designing policies to mitigate the agricultural contribution to climate change: an assessment of soil based carbon sequestration and its ancillary effects. <i>Climatic Change</i> 105, 43-66.
15	Haley, S., 2006.	Sugar and Sweeteners Outlook/SSS-246/May 30 2006. In: <i>Economic Research Service (Ed.)</i> , USDA.
16	Hansen, L., Hellerstein, D., 2007.	The value of the reservoir services gained with soil conservation. <i>Land Econ</i> 83, 285-301.
17	Holmes, T.P., 1987.	The Off-Site Impact of Soil-Erosion on Water-Treatment Costs - a Hedonic Function-Approach. <i>Am J Agr Econ</i> 69, 1092-1092.
18	Jasinski, S.M., 2000.	Peat. <i>US Geological Survey Minerals Yearbook</i> . US Geological Survey.

Ref	Authors, Year of publication	Title, Place of publication
19	Kay, S., Graves, A., Palma, J. H., Moreno, G., Rocas-Díaz, J. V., Aviron, S., Chouvardas, D., Crous-Duran, J., Ferreiro-Domínguez, N., García de Jalón, S., Măcicășan, V., Mosquera-Losada, M.R., Pantera, A., Santiago-Freijanes, J.J., Szerencsits, E., Torralba, M., Burgess, P.J., Herzog, F., 2019	Agroforestry is paying off—Economic evaluation of ecosystem services in European landscapes with and without agroforestry systems. <i>Ecosystem services</i> , 36, 100896.
20	Miranowski, J.A., Hammes, B.D., 1984.	Implicit Prices of Soil Characteristics for Farmland in Iowa. <i>Am J Agr Econ</i> 66, 745-749.
21	Moore, W.B., McCarl, B.A., 1987.	Off-Site Costs of Soil Erosion: A Case Study in the Willamette Valley. <i>Western Journal of Agricultural Economics</i> 12, 42-49.
22	Nkonya, E., Gicheru, P., Woelcke, J., Okoba, B., Kilambya, D., Gachimbi, L.N., 2008.	On-Site and Off-Site Long-Term Economic Impacts of Soil Fertility Management Practices. IFPRI Discussion Paper 00778.
23	Noel, J.E., Qenani-Petrela, E., Mastin, T., 2008.	A Benefit Transfer Approach to the Estimation of Agro-Ecosystems Services Values. <i>J Agr Resour Econ</i> 33, 489-489.
24	Pimentel, D., Harvey, C., Resosudarmo, P., Sinclair, K., Kurz, D., McNair, M., Crist, S., Shpritz, L., Fitton, L., Saffouri, R., Blair, R., 1995.	Environmental and Economic Costs of Soil Erosion and Conservation Benefits. <i>Science</i> 267, 1117-1123.
25	Pimentel, D., Wilson, C., McCullum, C., Huang, R., Dwen, P., Flack, J., Tran, Q., Saltman, T., Cliff, B., 1997.	Economic and environmental benefits of biodiversity. <i>Bioscience</i> 47, 747-757.
26	Porter, J., Costanza, R., Sandhu, H., Sigsgaard, L., Wratten, S., 2009.	The Value of Producing Food, Energy, and Ecosystem Services within an Agro-Ecosystem. <i>Ambio</i> 38, 186-193.
27	Pretty, J.N., Brett, C., Gee, D., Hine, R.E., Mason, C.F., Morison, J.I.L., Raven, H., Rayment, M.D., van der Bijl, G., 2000.	An assessment of the total external costs of UK agriculture. <i>Agr Syst</i> 65, 113-136.
28	Rodríguez-Entrena, M., Barreiro-Hurle, J., Gomez-Limon, J.A., Espinosa-Goded, M., Castro-Rodríguez, J., 2012.	Evaluating the demand for carbon sequestration in olive grove soils as a strategy toward mitigating climate change. <i>Journal of Environmental Management</i> 112, 368-376
29	San, C.C., Rapera, C.L., 2010.	The On-site Cost of Soil Erosion by the Replacement Cost Methods in Inle Lake Watershed, Nyaung Shwe Township, Myanmar. <i>J Environ Sci Manag</i> 13, 67-81.
30	Sandhu, H.S., Wratten, S.D., Cullen, R., Case, B., 2008.	The future of farming: The value of ecosystem services in conventional and organic arable land. An experimental approach. <i>Ecological Economics</i> 64, 835-848.
31	Scott, C.A., Zarazúa, J.A., Levine, G., 2000.	Urban-Wastewater Reuse for Crop Production in the Water-Short Guanajuato River Basin, Mexico. <i>International Water Management Institute</i> .

Ref	Authors, Year of publication	Title, Place of publication
32	Tegtmeier, E.M., Duffy, M.D., 2005.	External Costs of Agricultural Production in the United States. <i>Int J Agr Sustain</i> 2, 1-20.
33	van der Putten, W.H., Anderson, J.M., Bardgett, R.D., Behan-Pelletier, V., E. Bignell, D., Brown, G.G., Brown, V.K., Brussaard, L., Hunt, H.W., Ineson, P., Jones, T.H., Lavelle, P., Paul, E.A., John, M.S., Wardle, D.A., Wojtowicz, T., Wall, D.H.(Eds.), 2004.	The sustainable delivery of goods and services provided by soil biota. Island Press, San Francisco, Ca
34	Virta, R.L., 2004.	Clay and Shale. US Geological Survey Minerals Yearbook. US Geological Survey.
35	Xiao, Y., Xie, G.D., Lu, C.X., Ding, X.Z., Lu, Y., 2005.	The value of gas exchange as a service by rice paddies in suburban Shanghai, PR China. <i>Agr Ecosyst Environ</i> 109, 273-283.
36	Bernues, A., T. Rodriguez-Ortega, F. Alfnes, M. Clemetsen and L. O. Eik, 2015	Quantifying the Multifunctionality of Fjord and Mountain Agriculture by Means of Sociocultural and Economic Valuation of Ecosystem Services, <i>Land Use Policy</i> 48, pp. 170-178
37	Chaikaew, P., A.W. Hodges and S. Grunwald, 2017	Estimating the Value of Ecosystem Services in a Mixed-Use Watershed: A Choice Experiment Approach, <i>Ecosystem Services</i> 23, pp. 228-237
38	Dominati, E. J.; Mackay, A.; Bouma, J.; Green, S., 2016	An ecosystems approach to quantify soil performance for multiple outcomes: The future of land evaluation?
39	Sandhu, H., Wratten, S., & Cullen, R. 2010	The role of supporting ecosystem services in conventional and organic arable farmland. <i>Ecological Complexity</i> , 7, 302–310. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecocom.2010.04.006
40	Ibarra, A. A., Zambrano, L., Valiente, E., & Ramos-Beuno, A., 2013	Enhancing the potential value of environmental services in urban wetlands: An agro-ecosystem approach. <i>Cities</i> , 31, 438–443. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2012.08.002
41	Jónsson, J. Ö. G., Daviosdottir, B., & Nikolaidis, N. P., 2016	Valuation of Soil Ecosystem Services. In <i>Quantifying and managing soil functions in Earth's critical zone: combining experimentation and mathematical modelling</i> (Vol. 142, pp. 353–384). Elsevier.
42	Sandhu, H., Wratten, S., Costanza, R., Pretty, J., Porter, J., & Reganold, J., 2015	Significance and value of non-traded ecosystem services on farmland. <i>PeerJ</i> , 22. https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.762
43	Naranjo, S., Ellsworth, P., & Frisvold, G., 2015	Economic Value of Biological Control in Integrated Pest Management of Managed Plant Systems. <i>Annual Review of Entomology</i> , 60, 621–645. https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-ento-010814-021005

6.2 Annual ESS flows in EUR - after treatment

Table 7: Annual ESS flows in EUR - after mechanical amelioration (DLC)

Region	Provision of food, feed and fibre	Carbon storage	Water retention and plant water availability	Filtering of nutrients	Soil formation	Nutrient and organic compounds cycling	SUM
BB	106,243,540	9,890,779	2,743,646	-85,509,644	1,989,572	339,304,182	374,662,075
BW	85,812,090	7,988,706	2,216,022	-69,065,482	1,606,962	274,053,377	302,611,676
BY	214,530,225	19,971,765	5,540,054	-172,663,704	4,017,406	685,133,444	756,529,190
HE	59,251,205	5,516,011	1,530,110	-47,688,071	1,109,569	189,227,332	208,946,157
MV	46,992,335	4,374,768	1,213,536	-37,821,573	880,003	150,076,850	165,715,918
NI	83,768,945	7,798,499	2,163,259	-67,421,065	1,568,701	267,528,297	295,406,636
NW	49,035,480	4,564,975	1,266,298	-39,465,989	918,264	156,601,930	172,920,958
RP	42,906,045	3,994,353	1,108,011	-34,532,741	803,481	137,026,689	151,305,838
SH	20,431,450	1,902,073	527,624	-16,444,162	382,610	65,250,804	72,050,399
SL	10,215,725	951,036	263,812	-8,222,081	191,305	32,625,402	36,025,200
SN	28,604,030	2,662,902	738,674	-23,021,827	535,654	91,351,126	100,870,559
ST	85,812,090	7,988,706	2,216,022	-69,065,482	1,606,962	274,053,377	302,611,676
TH	73,553,220	6,847,462	1,899,447	-59,198,984	1,377,396	234,902,895	259,381,437
DE (sum)	907,156,380	84,452,037	23,426,514	-730,120,805	16,987,888	2,897,135,704	3,199,037,717

Table 8: Annual ESS flows in EUR - after biological amelioration (cultivation of alfalfa)

Region	Provision of food, feed and fibre	Carbon storage	Water retention and plant water availability	Filtering of nutrients	Soil formation	Nutrient and organic compounds cycling	SUM
BB	2,553,931	305,690	3,112,983	-7,999,863	1,147,830	16,312,701	15,433,273
BW	18,899,091	2,262,108	23,036,072	-59,198,984	8,493,944	120,713,988	114,206,218
BY	42,395,259	5,074,459	51,675,512	-132,797,721	19,053,982	270,790,837	256,192,328
HE	10,215,725	1,222,761	12,451,931	-31,999,451	4,591,321	65,250,804	61,733,091
MV	2,553,931	305,690	3,112,983	-7,999,863	1,147,830	16,312,701	15,433,273
NI	8,172,580	978,209	9,961,544	-25,599,561	3,673,057	52,200,643	49,386,473
NW	10,215,725	1,222,761	12,451,931	-31,999,451	4,591,321	65,250,804	61,733,091
RP	5,618,649	672,519	6,848,562	-17,599,698	2,525,227	35,887,942	33,953,200
SH	3,064,718	366,828	3,735,579	-9,599,835	1,377,396	19,575,241	18,519,927
SL	2,553,931	305,690	3,112,983	-7,999,863	1,147,830	16,312,701	15,433,273
SN	6,129,435	733,657	7,471,158	-19,199,671	2,754,793	39,150,482	37,039,855
ST	8,683,366	1,039,347	10,584,141	-27,199,533	3,902,623	55,463,184	52,473,127
TH	10,215,725	1,222,761	12,451,931	-31,999,451	4,591,321	65,250,804	61,733,091
DE (sum)	131,272,066	15,712,481	160,007,308	-411,192,944	58,998,475	838,472,833	793,270,219

Previous publications

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